

Basic Tests of Potato Yield Monitoring Sensors for Small-Sized Korean Harvesters

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Introduction

- ❖ Precision agriculture technologies(real-time yield monitoring sensors): demanding by female and aged farmers
- ❖ Mechanization rate of dryland crop production in Korea: 56%
- ❖ Need to develop precision agriculture appropriate for Korean working environment
- ❖ Purpose of the study: To conduct basic tests of yield monitoring sensors for small-sized Korean potato harvesters

Materials and Methods

❖ Potato yield monitoring system design

Schematic diagram of the Potato yield monitoring system

Test bench of the yield monitoring sensors for the basic test

❖ Sensor module

Sensor	Specification	
	Production Company	Bonsin
	Rated capacity	10 kg
	Rated power	2.0 mV/V
	Impressed voltage	10 ~ 15 V
	Input/Output register	410/350 Ohms
	Production Company	Baumer
	Type	1/3" progressive scan CCD, global shutter
	Resolution	1288 x 960 px
	Exposure time	0,004 ~ 60,000 ms
	Voltage supply range	12 ~ 24 V DC

Results and Discussion

❖ Load cell

Sensor output by height between the impact plate and the potato

❖ Image processing

Image processing of potato (up) and output of CCD camera (down)

Conclusions

- ❖ The average calculated weight by load cell
 - 0 cm: 228.5 ± 50.8 g
 - 10 cm: 232.1 ± 43.7
 - 20 cm: 236.6 ± 50.4
 - 30 cm: 236.7 ± 50.3
 - 40 cm: 236.5 ± 49.7
- ❖ The average calculated weight of image processing: 235.7 ± 50.31
- ❖ Both of the mass flow and volume flow approaches showed promising results.
- ❖ Further tests should be conducted to minimize the effects of vibration and slope of the test body, especially considering the harvesting field conditions.

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